

of ground mycelia within a day. The procedure is outlined below.

Grow hyphal cultures in 50 ml of Fries medium in 125-ml flasks at 30 °C with shaking. After 5-10 d, harvest the mycelia by suction and lyophilize them. Grind the dried mycelia finely using a mortar and pestle with liquid N or, alternatively, with a few grains of sterile acid-washed sand. If stored at -20 °C with a desiccant, the mycelial powder will keep for several months.

For a single extraction, suspend 50-75 mg of pulverized mycelia in 750 µl extraction buffer (100 mM Tris-HCl, pH 8; 100 mM EDTA; and 250 mM NaCl) by light vortexing in a 1.5-ml microcentrifuge tube. The needed amount of mycelia powder will fill about a quarter of the tube. Add 75 µl 10% (wt/vol) SDS; mix the contents gently and incubate for at least 30 min at 65 °C. Then add 300 µl potassium acetate solution (3 M potassium acetate-2 M acetic acid, pH 4.8), mix gently by inversion, and incubate the tube on ice for 15 min. Spin down precipitate (proteins and detergent) and debris at 13,000 rpm for 15 min.

Carefully transfer 750 µl of supernatant to a fresh tube containing 750 µl 2-propanol. (If a cleaner preparation is needed, the supernatant may be extracted with an equal volume of 24:1 (vol/vol) chloroform-isoamyl alcohol prior to alcohol precipitation.) Invert the tube to mix. Keep the tube on ice for 10 min, or longer if precipitation of nucleic acids is not satisfactory. Pellet down the nucleic acid (13,000 rpm for 5 min), wash with 70% ethanol, air-dry, and resuspend in 40 µl of TE buffer (10 mM Tris-HCl, pH 7.5-8; and 1 mM EDTA). This procedure will yield about 15 µg of DNA.

For a single Southern hybridization, use 1-3 µg of DNA per lane. DNA stored at 4 °C or lower will remain stable in TE buffer for several months. Contaminating RNA can be eliminated with RNase A (20 ng/µl final concentration) either during or after DNA restriction digestion. ■

Sclerotia of false smut (FSm) of rice from Assam, India

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Sclerotia of FSm *Claviceps oryzae sativae* Hashioka were found in Assam for the first time in late Nov 1991.

Less than 1% of the FSm spore balls in a rainfed lowland winter rice (Jul-Dec) crop had the sclerotia. They were borne as peelings from the surface of some spore balls and looked like petals of a flower bud (Fig. 1). Two sclerotia usually developed on a spore ball. They were never formed inside the spore balls.

Sclerotia were shed easily and were collected from the ground near rice hills. The largest sclerotium measured 14 × 7 mm, the smallest was 5 × 3 mm (Fig. 2).

The maximum and minimum temperatures during the week in which sclerotia developed ranged from 20 to 26 °C and from 11 to 15 °C, respectively. The relatively low temperatures during late Nov to early Dec induced sclerotia formation.

The sclerotia germinated after 3 mo when buried in sterile moist sand. They produced stalked stroma with plenty of ascospores.

FSm sclerotia were earlier reported in India at altitudes of 1,200 m and above in the hilly regions of the north where

1. Sclerotia of FSm borne on spore ball.

2. Sclerotia of FSm detached from spore ball.

temperate climate prevails. The sclerotia recently observed are in the plains region (Jorhat) at an altitude of 91 m. Sclerotia, through ascospores, can cause primary infection of rice. ■

A rapid method for DNA fingerprinting of the rice blast fungus *Pyricularia grisea*

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DNA fingerprinting and phylogenetic analysis based on the repetitive DNA probe MGR586 (Dupont) have been useful in studying the population structure of the rice blast fungus *P. grisea*. The DNA fingerprints are used to group isolates according to genetic similarity. The inference is that the groups share a common ancestor and,

Association between groups of isolates defined by RAPD (primer J-06) and RFLP (probe MGR586).^a

RFLP (MGR586)	RAPD (J-06)	Isolates (no.)
1, 1c, 1d, 1e	1	24
7, 7a	2	12
4, 4a, 4b, 4c	3, 4, 5	69
2	6	1
3	7	5
9	8	1
11	9	1
14	10	5
10	11	1
13	12	1

^aMGR586 designations with the same number and different letters are very similar but not identical (80% of bands in common). Each distinct profile produced by RAPD (J-06) was given a different number. Designations for groups of isolates are arbitrary.

RFLP (MGR 586 types)

DNA profiles generated by a) RFLP MGR 586 and b) RAPD (J-06). M = DNA molecular weight markers.

given the asexual propagation of the pathogen, therefore belong to one lineage.

The restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP) technique, however, is time-consuming and expensive, involving restriction endonuclease digestion, agarose gel electrophoresis, Southern blotting, DNA hybridization, and detection. A simplified DNA technique could allow greater efficiency in characterizing pathogen populations.

We tried a polymerase chain reaction (PCR)-based technique termed randomly amplified polymorphic DNA (RAPD). It is faster and simpler than RFLP and allows in vitro synthesis or amplification of random DNA segments that are determined by single primers of arbitrary nucleotide sequence. The amplified products are then electrophoresed in 2% agarose and DNA polymorphism can be detected by examining the ethidium bromide-stained gel under UV light.

When twenty-seven 10-base primers (Operon Technologies) were randomly selected and screened; 17 showed polymorphism among five diverse strains of *P. grisea*. Primer J-06 (5' TCGTTCCGCA 3') generated clear DNA profiles and defined groups of isolates that corresponded well with the groupings generated by repetitive DNA probe MGR586 for 120 isolates collected from Cavinti, Laguna, Philippines, and from IRRI-blast nursery upland screening sites (see table). Each distinct MGR lineage corresponded to one or a few RAPD (J-06) types. The DNA fingerprints generated by the two methods are shown in the figure.

RAPD (J-06) is faster than RFLP (MGR586) analysis, but it is less informative for phylogenetic analysis because fewer bands are produced for each isolate. Because corresponding groups of isolates are defined with

MGR586 and RAPD (J-06) for the Philippine isolates tested, we propose that the two methods be used together to improve the overall efficiency with which field populations of the pathogen can be analyzed. A preliminary survey using

RAPD can be used to group similar strains and reduce redundancy. All distinct groups can then be sampled adequately for MGR586 analysis to establish the relationships among strains and lineages. ■

Rice dwarf (RD), a new virus disease in the Philippines

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RD is a destructive virus disease that was known to occur only in temperate regions such as Japan, Korea, China, and Nepal.

RD disease symptoms were recently observed in ricefields in Midsayap, North Cotabato, Philippines. Infected plants showed stunting and fine chlorotic specks or streaks on leaf blades (Fig. 1). Most of the plants showing the chlorotic specks were also infected with tungro disease, which obscures the symptoms of RD. However, RD leaf symptoms were clearly visible in plants infected with rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) only.

Serological tests and electron microscopy confirmed RD infection in plant samples collected from Midsayap. Leaf extracts from symptomatic leaves diluted up to a thousand times gave a strong positive reaction to RD virus

1. RDV-infected leaves showing chlorotic specks or streaks (right); healthy leaf (extreme left).

2. a) RDV particles (arrows); b) RDV and RTBV particles.

(RDV) antiserum in rapid immunofilter paper assay. Electron microscopic observations of clarified infected sap revealed the presence of RDV particles (Fig. 2a), the diameter of which (65 nm)

is about twice that of RTBV (Fig. 2b).

RD was reported in the Philippines in the past, but the case was later proven to be tungro. Hence, this is the first true identification of RD in the Philippines. ■

Integrated pest management—weeds

Weed control in upland ricefields of Karnataka

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Weeds are a big constraint to raising the average upland rice yield in Karnataka from the current low of about 1 t/ha. Hand weeding is very effective but requires a lot of labor, thus making it costly for the upland farmer. Suitable herbicides have not yet been found.

To determine effective and economical weed control practices, we experimented during 1989-91 kharif by combining herbicides or using them with cultural practices. Butachlor and pendimethalin were applied alone or in combination with 2,4-D or hand weeding (Table 1). A weed-free treatment, two hand weedings at 20 and 40 d after rice emergence (DE), and nonweeded treatment were used for comparison. Plots were hand weeded in the weed-free check.

The trial was laid out in a randomized complete block design. Soil is silty clay loam with pH 7.0, 0.84% organic C, and

an average 0.6 kg P/ha and 114.1 kg K/ha. Avinash in 1989 and 1990 and IET5656 in 1991 were seeded at 100 kg/ha with a spacing of 20 cm between rows. Fertilizer was applied 100-10.9-20.7 kg NPK/ha.

We took weed samples from a 1-m² quadrat and weighed them at the heading stage of the grassy weeds. We recorded yield and yield components from a 5-m² net plot area. Common weeds were *Echinochloa colona*, *Panicum* spp., *Digitaria* sp., *Ischaemum rugosum*, *Cyperus iria*, *C. rotundus*, *C. difformis*, *Cyanotis* spp., *Commelina benghalensis*, *Spilanthes paniculata*, *Ageratum conyzoides*, and *Eclipta prostrata*.